

APPLYING ETHNOGRAPHIC APPROACHES IN CULTURE AND LANGUAGE TEACHING

Nematullaeva Muslimakhon Rakhmatullo kizi

Student of the third English language faculty, UzSWLU

e-mail: muslimanematullayeva797@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13892274>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 21-sentabr 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 23-sentabr 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 30-sentabr 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

culture and ethnography, language acquisition, culture education, communication skills.

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to considering the application of ethnographic approaches in teaching culture and language, highlighting the importance of understanding cultural contexts and social dynamics in the language learning process. The study utilizes qualitative and secondary data analysis methods, examining various existing scientific research to provide insights into how ethnography can enhance language instruction. By integrating ethnographic techniques, educators can foster a more contextually relevant language learning experience that goes beyond grammar and vocabulary to include cultural norms, values, and practices.

INTRODUCTION

This article is to highlight the use of ethnography as a tool for teaching language and culture to non-native English speakers. Initially, it discusses the concept of ethnography as introduced by Agar (1980), its origins, and its development over time. The article explores the role of culture and its intrinsic connection with language, citing Kramsch (1993) to emphasize the significance of ethnographic approaches in language education. The benefits of using ethnography are demonstrated through a sample activity designed by the author, which encourages language learners to investigate real-life interactions, thereby enhancing their observation and communication skills. This approach not only fosters linguistic competence but also deepens learners' understanding of cultural contexts, providing cultural learning and experience beyond language acquisition. A sample activity centered on Shrove Tuesday is also included, also known as Pancake Day, to illustrate the practical application of ethnography in language and culture instruction. The aim of this paper is to explore how ethnographic approaches can be effectively applied in the teaching and learning of language and culture. Although ethnography originated in anthropology, it has since been adopted by various disciplines, including language and culture education. As modern societies become increasingly diverse and multicultural, ethnographic methods have gained popularity and significance in language teaching. These approaches are particularly effective in current, multicultural contexts, making them a valuable tool for language and culture education in this globalized world.

METHODS

While conducting this research, qualitative and secondary data analysis methods were used to demonstrate impacts of teaching vowel sounds on improvement of students' pronunciation.

Culture and Ethnography

Culture is an abstract concept that encompasses a wide range of aspects. Ethnographic approaches to studying culture have been greatly influenced by poststructuralist views. Holliday (2013) characterizes culture as “whatever is around us and whatever has some sort of social behavior”. This aligns with Geertz's (1973) assertion that culture consists of socially established structures of meaning that guide people in their actions. Geertz further argues that culture can be viewed as a symbolic system where internal elements are identified and examined, and the system as a whole is understood through the relationships among these elements (Geertz, 1973).

The Connection of Language and Culture:

The Concept of Languaculture

Building on these ideas, I will now discuss the concept of “languaculture”, a term developed by Agar (1994) to highlight the link between language and culture. This idea originates from Kramsch's (1993) theory regarding the interconnection of language and culture. Kramsch contends that culture is a social construct, influenced by both self-perception and perceptions of others. She suggests that understanding a foreign culture involves reflecting on both the target culture (C2) and one's own culture (C1). To explain further, C1 represents the native culture; C1 is the perception of C1 from someone within the culture, while C1 is the perception of C1 from an outsider's perspective (Kramsch, 1993). Kramsch also notes that the understanding of C2 is deeply rooted in one's perception of C1. To avoid a limited understanding of both C1 and C2, she proposes developing a third perspective that allows language learners to adopt both insider and outsider viewpoints of C1 and C2. Agar (1994) introduces and expands on the concept of “languaculture”, a term derived from Friedrich's (1989) idea of “linguaculture”, which highlights the intrinsic connection between language and culture. Agar emphasizes that language encompasses more than just grammar and vocabulary; it also includes pragmatics, which refers to the broader context in which communication occurs, along with the personal traits of the speakers involved. As a result, Agar (1994) argues that language and culture are inseparably linked, and one cannot truly “know” a foreign language without understanding the culture in which it has developed. Agar describes culture as the interaction between two separate languacultures, which he calls LC1 (native languaculture) and LC2 (target languaculture).

RESULTS

Ethnography involves immersive observation and participation in the social and cultural contexts of the target language. In language teaching, ethnographic approaches can include activities such as participant observation, cultural immersion, field notes, and reflective journals. These methods help students engage with the language in real-life contexts, providing insights into how native speakers use language in everyday interactions, how cultural norms influence communication, and how language evolves within specific communities.

Participant Observation.

Participant observation allows learners to engage directly with the cultural and linguistic environment of the target language. By observing and participating in activities within a community, students gain firsthand experience of language use in various social settings. This method not only improves language skills but also enhances cultural awareness and empathy.

Cultural Immersion.

Immersion programs, such as study abroad or virtual exchanges, enable learners to experience the target culture and language simultaneously. Ethnographic techniques, such as documenting cultural experiences and reflecting on interactions, help students connect language learning with cultural understanding, fostering a deeper appreciation of the nuances in communication.

Field Notes and Reflective Journals.

Encouraging students to keep field notes and reflective journals during their language learning journey allows them to document their observations and reflect on cultural differences. This practice promotes critical thinking and self-awareness, enabling learners to analyze their own cultural assumptions and adapt their communication styles accordingly.

DISCUSSION

The concept of ethnography originates from anthropology in the late 19th century, when European anthropologists began to recognize it as the practice of systematically describing a community through observation by a participant observer who lives among the community members for an extended period, often months or years (Corbett, 2003, p. 19). As noted by Agar (1980, p. 69), ethnography involves deep personal engagement with the community and continuous observation. The research process may span several years, with a focus on direct personal involvement and understanding the behaviors of group members within the community, rather than merely predicting these behaviors (Agar, 1980). Barro, Jordan, and Roberts (1998) further define ethnography as “the study of other people and the social and cultural patterns that give meaning to their lives”. Ethnography is closely linked to the human element, as the ethnographer is responsible for collecting, validating, and analyzing data, making the research process highly dependent on the ethnographer’s skills and insights (Suwartono, 2014). Building on Barro et al.’s ideas about ethnography, Kaplan-Weinger and Ullman (2015) argue that knowledge is not solely held within individuals but rather resides within communities. They emphasize that it is through social interactions that people learn to behave in ways that are socially acceptable. According to Kaplan-Weinger and Ullman (2015), individuals acquire knowledge from their lived experiences. This perspective aligns with the idea that observations must be contextualized rather than viewed in isolation; understanding requires recognizing the broader context that shapes our language knowledge and connecting it with the new aspects of the situation where learning occurs (Agar, 1980). This approach has led to the application of ethnography in the field of language and culture teaching, highlighting the significant role of culture in shaping ethnographic methods in education.

CONCLUSION

Ethnographic studies provide a rich, contextualized understanding of language learning practices across different cultures. By exploring how cultural norms, social interactions, and educational structures shape language learning, these studies offer valuable insights for developing more effective and culturally sensitive language teaching methodologies. Recognizing the importance of cultural context in language learning can lead to more inclusive and effective educational practices that better meet the needs of diverse learners.

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